

Analysis of Induction Motor Used In Electric Vehicle Applications and Comparison of Copper Rotor Bars with Aluminium Rotor Bars Using Finite Element Method

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Abstract— In this article, induction motor analysis of Tesla Model S was made firstly and then two materials for rotor bars analysis and comparison were made for induction motor of Tesla Model S. These material types of rotor bars are aluminium and copper. The advantages and disadvantages of two different materials for induction motor rotor bars of Tesla Model S were compared. Finally, evaluations and inferences were made with the analyzes and comparisons made.

Keywords—Induction Motor, Aluminium Rotor Bars for Induction Motor , Copper Rotor Bars for Induction Motor, Analysis, Optimization, Finite Element Method, Electric Vehicle, ANSYS Motor-CAD

1 INTRODUCTION

Thus, the paper aims to analyze to induction motor of Tesla Model S as thermally and electromagnetically and compare Copper Rotor Bars with Aluminium Rotor Bars using finite element method with all the available data for Tesla Model S induction motor.

Today, the selection of the appropriate motor for the electric vehicle is very important in electric vehicle technology and the all parts of motor must be considered. The material selection for rotor bars is important part of design process for squirrel cage induction motor because the material effect to efficiency, temperature and weight of squirrel cage induction motor directly. The squirrel cage induction motor of Tesla Model S will be analysed and two rotors with rotor bars made of two different materials will be examined and compared. The advantages and disadvantages of these compared rotor types will be stated in the article. The first model is copper rotor bars type and second model is aluminium rotor bars type for squirrel cage induction motor. When we compare the aluminium

and copper, copper is 39% more electrically conductive than aluminium. On the other hand, aluminum is 70% lighter than copper. Therefore, aluminum material can be preferred in rotor bar material selection in application areas where motor weight is important and the cost is considerable. The density of annealed copper is 8.933g/cm^3 and melting at 1083°C , the density of cast aluminium is 2.95g/cm^3 and melting at $660,3^\circ\text{C}$. These datas are available in ANSYS Motor-CAD. The electrical resistivities of annealed copper and cast aluminium are $1,724 \times 10^{-8}\ \Omega\text{m}$ and $3,3 \times 10^{-8}\ \Omega\text{m}$ at 20°C and these resistivities of materials are known as reference resistivity of materials, the reference resistivity is important parameter to calculate resistance of material at any temperature. The “alpha” (α) constant is known as the temperature coefficient of resistance of materials, and symbolizes the resistance change factor per degree of temperature change, thermal coefficient of resistivity of annealed copper and cast aluminium are $3,93 \times 10^{-3}$ and $3,75 \times 10^{-3}$. The resistances of materials can be calculated at any temperature by equation (1).

$$R = R_{ref}[1 + \alpha(T - T_{ref})] \quad (1)$$

where

R is the resistances of materials at temperature “T”, R_{ref} is electrical resistivity of material at 20°C , α is temperature coefficient of resistance as $1/^\circ\text{C}$ and T is temperature as $^\circ\text{C}$.

2 IDENTICAL STATOR PARAMETERS FOR ALL MOTOR MODELS

The geometric parameters of stator are same for two models in this article and these geometric parameters were shown in Table 1 and 2D view of stator shown in

Fig.3.The diameter of the pure copper is 1.1 mm and stacking factor for stator core is 0.95.

Parameters	Units	Values
Stator Outer Diameter	mm	254
Stator Inner Diameter	mm	157
Stack Length of Stator	mm	152,6
Skew of Stator	mm	0
Slot Number of Stator	/	60
Conductors Per Slot	/	52
Number of Strands	/	26
Slot Fill Factor	%	37,00
Number of Turns	/	1
Tooth Width	mm	4
Slot Depth	mm	19
Slot Opening	mm	2,9

Table 1:Geometric parameters of stator

2.1 WINDING PATTERN DESIGN OF IDENTICAL STATOR

The winding pattern of stator is designed with given parameters of induction motor of Tesla Model S .The winding pattern consists of a concentric set of 3 coils per pole and per phase, with a coil pitch of 10-12-14 and turns per coil of 1-2-2 and it has 2 parallel branches and 2 winding layers [5].The winding pattern is shown in Fig.2 and 1.phase wire colours are red and pink, 2.phase wire colours are green and teal and 3.phase wire colours are navy blue and lighth blue in this pattern.

Fig.2.Winding pattern of stator

3 GENERAL DATAS OF MOTOR

The motor used by Tesla company for Model S is a four poles squirrel cage induction motor [1]. The length of motor is 280 mm. The conductive rods inside squirrel cage

of the rotor is made of pure copper. The information could not be found about the electrical steel used by Tesla. That's why M250-35A non grain oriented electrical steel sheets are used for the modeling of the motor and the stacking factor of rotor and stator is 0.95. The airgap distance of motor is 0.5 mm. The cooling system is made of the stator and rotor of motor, the stator is cooled using a classical water jacket and the heat is extracted from the rotor using a spiral shaft Groove. The housing diameter is 280 mm [1],[2],[3]. The thermal model of motor did not consider in the analysis. The analysis in this paper focused to the comparison of rotor bar materiel types for identical stator frame and 2-D axial view of motor is shown in Fig.4. The design parameters of rotor were shown in Table 3 [4],[5].

Parameters	Units	Values
Rotor Outer Diameter	mm	156,5
Rotor Inner Diameter	mm	50
Stack length of Rotor	mm	153,8
Skew of Rotor	mm	1,5
Slot Number of Rotor	/	74
Bar Depth	mm	23,87
Number of Poles	/	4

Table 3: Geometric parameters of rotor

Fig.3.IM 2D radial view

Fig.4.IM 2D axial view

4 GENERAL ANALYSIS OF MOTOR

The squirrel cage induction motor of Tesla Model S can deliver power up to 225 kW, with a maximum torque of 430 Nm and a maximum speed of 15000 rpm [3]. The maximum mechanical power can also calculate with equation 1 and the input can be calculated with efficiency of motor.

$$T_m = \frac{30 \cdot P_m}{\pi \cdot n} \quad (1)$$

where

T_m , P_m , and n mechanical torque, mechanical output power and rotational speed of motor.

The simulation parameters of motor were shown in Table 4.

Parameters	Units	Values
Operation Rotational Speed	rpm	4878
Frequency	Hz	166,7
Inverter Fed DC Bus Voltage	V	366
Peak Stator rms Current	A	900
Slip	%	2,45

Table 4: The analysis parameters of motor

The synchronous speed can be calculated with equation 2

$$S = \frac{N_s - N_o}{N_s} \quad (2)$$

where

N_s is synchronous speed, S is slip and N_o is operation speed. The synchronous speed is found as 4997.4 rpm when it is calculated with equation 2.

5 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS RESULTS OF FIRST MODEL

The analysis is completed with using ANSYS Motor-CAD software. The maximum torque per amper control method is selected to drive motor. The maximum temperatures of rotor cage and stator winding were set as 150°C and 180°C

at the beginning of analysis, which represents industrial insulation class F and operation temperatures of stator winding, rotor bar and end ring were set as 100°C [5]. The saturation model is created as FEA in the ANSYS Motor-CAD. The base(referance) speed of machine is observed as 6800 rpm, the maximum torque of motor decreased after this speed and the maximum torque is observed as 441 Nm untill base speed, these were shown in Fig.5 and Fig.6. The mechanical power and current is observed as 314.3 kW and 900 A at the base speed. The motor must supply with 332.1 kW and 230.2 Hz to achieve maximum torque base speed operation region. The power factor, total losses and efficiency of motor was observed as 0.8504, 15.65 kW and %94.64 at maximum torque base speed operation region. The 2D finite element flux density distribution map at the maximum torque base speed operation region of motor is shown in Fig.7 and the airgap mean flux density is observed as 0,7351 T. The output torque value increases when the airgap magnetic flux density of the motor increases and the amount of iron required in the rotor and stator lamination also increases. If this amount is not increased, the motor heats up. This will reduce the slot area required for the stator winding. On the other hand, as the air gap flux density increases, the number of turns required for the winding decreases. The flux density value in which the ferromagnetic material used in the core of the rotor and stator saturates is important. This value can be observed from the B-H curve of the material used.

Fig.5.FE model Efficiency map of first model

Fig.6.FE model mechanical power map of first model

Fig.7. 2D FE model with flux density levels and field lines of first model

The supply power is limited for Tesla Model S. Therefore, we can't operate to the machine on maximum torque base speed operation region. The motor can operate at maximum normal operation region. The maximum power is 225,13 kW, maximum torque is 443,27 Nm, the maximum speed is 4850 rpm at maximum torque, efficiency is %93.2 and power factor is 0,8485 at this region. On the other hand, the maximum speed and torque are 15000 rpm and 138 Nm. The efficiency, power factor and total losses are %95.87, 0,8835 and 15.08 kW at this region. The conductor losses of stator and rotor are the most significant loss component, it is 8.939 kW. The maximum normal operation region is shown in Fig.8.

Fig.8. Mechanical power map of the maximum normal operation region of first model

We can operate to the machine until yellow line, the maximum power limit exceeds and the motor could be damaged after this line.

The back EMF waveforms are smooth, they are shown in Fig.9 and the inductances are also important for motor operation characteristic at maximum normal operation region, they are shown in Fig.10. The rotor cage and total weight of motor are 6.663 kg and 64.39 kg.

Fig.9. Back EMF waveforms of first model

Fig.10. Inductances of first model

Fig.11. Total losses and rotor cage losses maps of first model

The total losses and rotor cage losses maps of motor at various operation regions were shown in Fig.11.

6 DESIGN AND ANALYSIS RESULTS OF SECOND MOTOR MODEL

The difference of the second model from the first model is that the conductor rods used in the rotor part use aluminum element instead of copper element. Conductor losses in the rotor increased as expected. The reason for this is that while aluminum's electrical conductivity is 3.4×10^7 , copper's is 5.8×10^7 . Considering the cost, copper is a more expensive element than aluminum. When we compare the prices of copper and aluminum elements, copper is much more expensive than aluminum. The plot of the changes in the prices of copper and aluminum elements from July-2017 to Jan-2021 is shown in Fig.12.

Fig.12. The price change plot of copper and aluminum elements [6]

Fig.13. Efficiency map of second model

The power factor of motor is observed 0.8504 and the total losses of machine was observed 15.65 kW and the efficiency was observed as %94.64 at maximum torque, base speed operation region.

Fig.14. Mechanical power map of the maximum normal operation region of second model

Fig.15. The total losses and rotor cage losses maps of second model

The weight of rotor cage reduced but the losses of rotor cage increased because of electrical conductivity of aluminum compare to copper.

Total weight and rotor cage weight of motor observed as 59.93 kg and 2.2 kg.

7 THERMAL ANALYSIS OF MODELS

The thermal analysis was applied for both model. The cooling system is divided into two parts for both model: the stator is cooled using a traditional water jacket and the heat from the rotor is extracted using a spiral shaft groove [2]. The results for both model were given in Fig.17 and Fig.18.

Fig.16. The lumped circuit nodal temperatures

Thermal analysis has been made for the first model, and the axial view of the motor with thermal analysis has been given on Fig.16. The average temperatures of the regions can be observed from the axial view.

Fig.17.The 2-D steady state thermal analysis of first model for rotor

Fig.18.The 2-D steady state thermal analysis of second model for rotor

As a result of the thermal analysis, it was observed that the first model was less heated as a result of the comparison of the two models. The reason for this is that the conductor losses are less for the copper conductor than for the aluminum conductor.

8 CONCLUSION

It is impossible to pick the best rotor material for every situation. The analysis shows that a squirrel cage induction motor with copper rotor bars has better performance than squirrel cage induction motor aluminum rotor bars as expected. Today, the cost of copper is important. Therefore, instead of the copper conductor bars inside the cage of the squirrel cage induction motor aluminum bars can be preferred various application because of the following advantages.

The weight of a squirrel cage induction motor with copper rotor bars is significantly heavier and more expensive in cost than a squirrel cage induction motor with aluminum rotor bars. However, as can be noticed from the efficiency maps of the first(Fig.5) and second model(Fig.13), the total losses are less, so squirrel cage induction motor with copper bars is much more efficient than squirrel cage induction motor with aluminum bars .

As a result, the entire significant advantages makes copper rotor bars are the best choice for implementation in the induction motor for the electric vehicle application in terms of efficiency and thermal.

DECLARATION

Conflict of interest on behalf of the author, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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